

RESEARCH & PUBLICATION ETHICS: AN EVALUATE

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ABSTRACT

Publication ethics are essential for maintaining the credibility of research publications. They involve preventing errors like fabrication, falsification, or misrepresentation of data, and upholding values such as social responsibility, human rights, and legal compliance. Authors are accountable for the quality and integrity of their work, while peer review helps validate research accuracy. Authorship criteria demand significant intellectual contributions to the study, and mere data collection may not suffice for authorship. Publishers must adhere to ethical standards in disseminating scholarly content, and authors should meet journal authorship criteria and undergo plagiarism checks. Editors ensure a fair peer-review process and avoid offensive language. Conflicts of interest can compromise the impartiality of authors, reviewers, and editors. Peer reviewers are external experts chosen by editors to enhance the quality of a study. Redundant publication occurs when multiple papers share the same content without proper referencing. Editors oversee journals, ensuring their success by guiding the journal, assembling a competent team, and considering stakeholders' needs. Editors should base acceptance decisions on importance, originality, clarity, and relevance. Misconduct involves intentionally deceiving others with false information. It is crucial to assess misconduct based on the act and the individual's intention, whether they are a researcher, author, editor, reviewer, or publisher. Editors have an ethical obligation to investigate and address potential misconduct cases rather than simply rejecting papers, though this can be challenging.

*Plagiarism can take different forms, such as not giving credit to others' ideas or passing off someone else's work as your own. It is essential to cite sources properly and obtain permission when using significant portions of others' content. Always attribute references to the original sources to avoid plagiarism. Be cautious of predatory journals that lack rigorous peer review processes and charge high publication fees. These journals may use deceptive tactics to attract authors, exploiting the author-pays open access model with minimal review and editing. Before submitting your work to an unfamiliar publisher, watch out for predatory practices like stand-alone journals, hijacked journals, and misleading metrics. While some journals may not meet the highest standards, they still follow reasonable processes in good faith. The "**Think. Check. Submit.**" website provides a checklist to help researchers identify reputable journals and publishers.*

Keywords: Research Ethics, Authors, Editors and Publishers Must Uphold Ethical Conduct, Conflicts of Interest, Peer Review, Redundant Publication, Plagiarism and Misconduct, Beware of Predatory Journals and Publishers.

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INTRODUCTION

Publication ethics are guidelines that govern the publication of scientific research and scholarly work, protecting intellectual property and preventing unauthorized republication. These guidelines are crucial as they promote research goals, truth, and error avoidance by prohibiting data fabrication, falsification, or misrepresentation. They also uphold values like trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness in collaborative work. Ethical norms ensure researchers can be held accountable to the public, garnering public support for research. Additionally, publication ethics promote moral and social values such as social responsibility, human rights, animal welfare, compliance with the law, and public health and safety, preventing harm to subjects and the public.

Authors have a crucial role in ensuring the integrity and quality of their research publications. Here are some key responsibilities that authors should uphold:

1. Review and verify the accuracy of calculations, data presentation, and results analysis in their research papers.
2. Conduct research ethically and in compliance with relevant regulations.
3. Follow the guidelines provided by the academic journal for peer review, editing, and publication.
4. Submit original manuscripts and avoid submitting the same paper to multiple journals.
5. Provide requested data, procedures, software, and other information to the editor promptly.
6. Clearly outline the research process and analysis methods to facilitate replication by other researchers.
7. Document procedures and results accurately and maintain systematic records for verification.
8. Disclose any limitations of the research.
9. Declare all financial and non-financial conflicts of interest for transparency.
10. Ensure the submitted manuscript is original and not published elsewhere.

11. Obtain permission from the copyright holder if re-publishing a previously published article.
 12. Include only individuals who have made significant contributions as co-authors.
- Adhering to these responsibilities helps maintain the credibility and ethical standards of academic publishing.

Role and Responsibilities of Publishers

Publishers have a crucial role in upholding publication ethics when disseminating scholarly content in journals. Here are some key responsibilities they should adhere to:

1. Authors must meet the journal's authorship criteria, and all eligible co-authors should be included.
2. Authors should provide a brief description of each author's contribution in the Acknowledgment section.
3. Corresponding authors must confirm that they have obtained written consent from all co-authors for the publication of the article.
4. Publishers should conduct plagiarism checks and inform authors of any issues.
5. Journal publishers should not manipulate journal metrics to artificially boost their journal's ranking.

Role and Responsibilities of Editors

1. Ensure fair, unbiased, and timely peer-review process.
2. Assign at least two external and independent reviewers for research articles.
3. Select reviewers with expertise in the relevant field for diverse and inclusive representation.
4. Evaluate manuscripts based on intellectual content, not on authors' personal characteristics.
5. Handle manuscripts confidentially and seek author's permission before disclosing details.
6. Ensure peer reviewers maintain confidentiality.
7. Request disclosure of conflicts of interest from peer reviewers.
8. Request citations from authors with a strong scholarly rationale.
9. Maintain confidentiality by not discussing the manuscript with others.
10. Provide supporting information for claims.
11. Refrain from using information from the manuscript in personal work before publication.
12. Only accept peer review assignments within expertise and reasonable timeframe.
13. Publish articles promptly.
14. Avoid using insulting, hostile, or defamatory language.

COMMITTEE ON PUBLICATION ETHICS (COPE)

Authorship Guidelines

Authorship is a critical aspect of research, and clear guidelines are essential to ensure fairness and accountability. Here are key points to consider:

1. Authorship Criteria: Authors should have made significant intellectual contributions to the study's conception, design, analysis, and writing. Merely collecting data may not be sufficient for authorship.

2. **Establishing Guidelines:** To prevent authorship disputes, it is advisable to set clear guidelines on authorship, contributions, and acknowledgments at the beginning of a research project.
3. **Public Responsibility:** All authors should be prepared to take public responsibility for the paper's content. Transparent communication of individual contributions can clarify each author's role.
4. **Journal Guidelines:** Review the target journal's "Advice to Authors" section to ensure compliance with their specific authorship requirements.

Adhering to these guidelines helps maintain research integrity and ensures proper credit for authors' contributions.

Conflicts of Interest

Conflicts of interest can affect the impartiality of authors, reviewers, and editors. These conflicts may arise from personal, commercial, political, academic, or financial connections. Financial conflicts can result from various sources, including employment, research funding, stock ownership, payment for lectures or travel, consultancies, and institutional support.

1. Researchers, authors, and reviewers must disclose any relevant conflicts of interest to the editors.
2. Editors should openly disclose any conflicts of interest to their audience. When unsure, it is best to err on the side of disclosure. In some cases, editors may need to recuse themselves from the review and decision-making process for a specific submission.

Peer Review

Peer reviewers are external experts selected by editors to provide feedback to improve the quality of a study. Journals have different review processes, some with open procedures where the reviewer's identity and report are revealed.

1. Authors' suggestions for potential reviewers can be helpful, but editors are not obligated to follow them.
2. Reviewers must maintain confidentiality when evaluating a manuscript and should not share it with colleagues without the editor's permission.
3. Avoid keeping or copying the submitted manuscript.
4. Reviewers and editors should not use the data, arguments, or interpretations without the authors' consent.
5. Reviewers are expected to provide timely, accurate, respectful, unbiased, and well-reasoned assessments.
6. If reviewers suspect misconduct, they should confidentially report it to the editor.
7. Journals should provide clear information about their peer review, selection, and appeals processes.
8. Journals should monitor their acceptance rates and publication timelines regularly.

Redundant Publication

Redundant publication happens when multiple papers cover the same hypothesis, data, discussion points, or conclusions without proper cross-referencing.

1. Avoid duplicating published studies unless additional verification is needed.
2. Publishing an abstract in meeting proceedings does not prevent full publication later, but previous publication should be acknowledged.
3. Republishing a paper in another language is acceptable if the original source is clearly cited.
4. Authors must disclose related papers, even if in a different language or if similar papers are in press, at the time of submission.

Editors Responsibilities

Editors play a crucial role in the success of journals by guiding the publication process and ensuring the quality of content. Their duties include:

1. Making acceptance decisions based on the significance, originality, clarity, and relevance of the paper.
2. Thoroughly assessing research that challenges existing findings.
3. Including studies with negative results to avoid publication bias.
4. Subjecting all original studies to peer review to address potential biases.
5. Safeguarding the confidentiality of submitted papers.
6. Addressing major flaws in published papers promptly.

Dealing with Misconduct

Principles:

1. Misconduct is confirmed when there is an intention to deceive others by presenting false information.
2. It is essential to evaluate misconduct based on both the action and the intention of the individual involved, whether they are a researcher, author, editor, reviewer, or publisher.
3. Deception can be intentional, reckless, or negligent. Therefore, complete honesty and full disclosure are crucial.
4. Codes of practice can increase awareness but may not cover all possible situations.

Investigating Misconduct

Editors are ethically obligated to investigate and address potential misconduct cases rather than simply rejecting problematic papers. However, this process can be complex. COPE can provide guidance on anonymized cases due to legal constraints. Ultimately, the editor has the discretion to determine the best course of action.

Dealing with Serious Misconduct

1. Editors must take all allegations of misconduct seriously, but they may not have the authority or resources to conduct thorough investigations.
2. The editor must decide when to notify the employers of the accused author(s).
3. Employers should have a process in place to investigate accusations, relieving editors of the burden of gathering a complete case. It may be ethically questionable for editors to do so, as it involves consulting experts and raising serious questions about the author(s).
4. If editors receive compelling evidence of serious misconduct, they should promptly inform the author(s) and provide the evidence to the employers.

5. In cases of serious misconduct allegations without convincing evidence, editors should seek confidential expert advice.
6. If experts express serious concerns about the research, editors should inform the employers.
7. If no misconduct is discovered, editorial processes should proceed as usual.
8. In cases of compelling evidence of serious misconduct with no employer to report to, registered doctors can refer the case to the General Medical Council.
9. If there is no legitimate organization available to conduct an investigation, the editor may choose to publish a statement in the journal if the case is deemed significant. Legal advice will be required in this scenario.
10. Editors may choose to publish a notice in the journal if they believe an employer has not adequately investigated a serious accusation. Legal guidance is essential.
11. Authors should be given the opportunity to address allegations of serious misconduct.

Less Serious Misconduct

1. Employers may not need to be involved in cases of less serious misconduct, such as redundant publication, deception over authorship, or failure to declare a conflict of interest. However, appointing an independent expert for review could be beneficial.
2. Editors should weigh the potential impact of minor misconduct accusations on authors and may involve their employers in investigations.
3. Authors should have the chance to address allegations of minor misconduct.
4. If misconduct is verified, editors may opt to impose sanctions from the following list:
 - Issuing a warning
 - Requiring a correction or retraction
 - Imposing a temporary ban on submission
 - Notifying the author's institution or funding body

Plagiarism

Plagiarism can take different forms, like not acknowledging others' ideas, claiming someone else's work as your own, or translating a document into another language and presenting it as original. It can happen at any point in the research and publishing process, whether in print or online.

Action: Always cite sources correctly and obtain permission when using significant portions of others' written or visual content.

Plagiarism Detection, Reporting, and Handling

If any member of the academic community suspects plagiarism in a document, they should report it to the Departmental Academic Integrity Panel (DAIP). The DAIP will investigate and provide recommendations to the Institutional Academic Integrity Panel (IAIP) of the HEI. The authorities of the HEI can also take suo motu notice of an act of plagiarism and initiate proceedings under these regulations. The HEI authorities can also take action on their own or based on examiner findings. All cases will be reviewed by the IAIP.

Departmental Academic Integrity Panel (DAIP)

i. All departments in the HEI must notify a DAIP with the following composition:

Chairman	Head of the Department	Members will serve for two years for points 'b' and 'c'. The quorum for meetings will be 2 out of 3 members, including the Chairman.
Member (b)	A senior academician from another department will be nominated by the head of the HEI.	
Member (c)	A person knowledgeable about anti-plagiarism tools, nominated by the Head of the Department.	

ii. The DAIP will follow the principles of natural justice when investigating plagiarism allegations involving students, faculty, researchers, and staff.

iii. The DAIP has the authority to evaluate plagiarism and recommend suitable penalties.

iv. After the investigation, the DAIP will submit a report with penalty recommendations to the IAIP within 45 days of receiving the complaint or initiating proceedings.

Institutional Academic Integrity Panel (IAIP)

i. HEI will notify an IAIP with the following composition:

Chairman	Pro-VC/Dean/Senior Academician of the HEI.	The Chairman of DAIP and IAIP cannot be the same person. The Committee members, including the Chairman, will serve a three-year term. A quorum for meetings will consist of at least 3 out of 4 members, including the Chairman.
Member	A senior academician, nominated by the Head of the HEI, will serve as the Chairman.	
Member	One external member nominated by the Head of the Higher Education Institution (HEI).	
Member	A person knowledgeable about anti-plagiarism tools, nominated by the Head of the HEI.	

ii. The IAIP will consider the DAIP recommendations.

iii. The IAIP will investigate plagiarism cases as per regulations.

iv. The IAIP will follow principles of natural justice in addressing plagiarism allegations involving students, faculty, researchers, and staff.

v. The IAIP can review DAIP's recommendations and penalties with justification.

vi. The IAIP will submit investigation reports and penalty recommendations to the HEI Head within 45 days of receiving DAIP's recommendation, complaint, or initiating proceedings.

vii. The IAIP will share a copy of the report with the individuals mentioned in the inquiry report.

Plagiarism Penalty for Students

Level - 0	Up to 10% Similarities	No Penalty
Level - 1	Above 10% to 40% Similarities	Such a student will be required to submit a revised script within a time period that cannot be exceeded by 6 months.
Level - 2	Above 40% to 60% Similarities	For one year, that student is banned from submitting a revised script.
Level - 3	Above 60% Similarities	Such student registration for that programme shall be cancelled.

Note 1: Penalty for repeated plagiarism: Students will face increased penalties for repeated instances of plagiarism. The severity of the punishment will escalate with each subsequent offense.

Note 2: Penalty for plagiarism after degree completion: If plagiarism is discovered after a student has already obtained their degree, the degree may be temporarily suspended based on the decision of the Institutional Academic Integrity Panel (IAIP) and Departmental Academic Integrity Panel (DAIP).

Plagiarism Penalty for Research Publications and Teaching Faculties

Level - 0	Up to 10% Similarities	No Penalty
Level - 1	Above 10% to 40% Similarities	Shall be asked to withdraw manuscript.
Level - 2	Above 40% to 60% Similarities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Shall be asked to withdraw manuscript. ✓ The right to one annual increment shall be denied. ✓ The individual is not permitted to supervise any new Master's, M.Phil., or Ph.D. student/scholar for a period of two years.
Level - 3	Above 60% Similarities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Shall be asked to withdraw manuscript. ✓ The right to two successive annual increments shall be denied. ✓ The individual is prohibited from supervising any new Master's, M.Phil. or Ph.D. student/scholar for a period of three years.

Note 1: Penalty for repeated plagiarism: Authors found guilty of repeated plagiarism will be required to withdraw their manuscript and face escalating penalties. If a level 3 offense is repeated, the Higher Education Institution (HEI) may take disciplinary action, including suspension or termination.

Note 2: Penalty for obtaining benefits through plagiarism: If plagiarism is discovered after obtaining benefits or credits, the individual's benefits or credits will be suspended for a specified period determined by IAIP and approved by the Head of the Institution.

Note 3: HEIs must implement a plagiarism detection system for all paper publications, theses, and dissertations submitted by students, faculty, researchers, or staff.

Note 4: In case of plagiarism allegations against the Head of an HEI, the Controlling Authority of the HEI will take appropriate action as per regulations.

Note 5: For complaints of plagiarism against Heads of Departments or other institutional authorities, IAIP will recommend suitable action, subject to approval by the Competent Authority.

Note 6: Members of DAIP or IAIP accused of plagiarism must recuse themselves from meetings where their case is being discussed or investigated.

Dos and Don'ts of Plagiarism

Here are some simple tips to follow:

Do:

- Attribute references to the original sources of information.
- Describe all sources of information and give acknowledgments.
- Provide footnotes to give additional context or information.
- Use quotation marks whenever you are directly quoting someone else's work.
- Paraphrase the original work and attribute it to the original author.
- If you are using extensive quotations, obtain permission from the publisher of the original work.
- Avoid self-plagiarism by obtaining permission from the publisher of any previous articles you have authored.
- Obtain permission for the use of published drawings or other illustrations.

Don't:

- Copy and paste text without proper attribution.
- Claim someone else's work as your own.
- Use someone else's ideas without giving credit.
- Rely solely on someone else's work without adding your own analysis or interpretation.
- Use copyrighted material without permission.
- Ignore citation guidelines and requirements.
- Plagiarize intentionally or unintentionally.

PREDATORY JOURNALS

Predatory journals are publications that solicit manuscripts from researchers, lack a peer review system, and often publish low-quality or worthless papers. These journals charge high publication fees and do not have a legitimate editorial board. The term "predatory journal" was coined by Jeffery Beall, a librarian at the University of Colorado, who observed a rise in exploitative academic journals charging author fees without maintaining proper quality standards. Predatory journals are also known as deceptive or scamming journals and are criticized for their poor academic standards.

Examples of predatory journals include:

1. International Journal of Digital Library Services (IJODLS)
2. International Journal of Research in Library Science (IJRLS)
3. Online Journal of Library & Information Science (OJLIS)

PREDATORY PUBLISHERS

Beware of predatory publishers that use deceptive tactics to lure authors by exploiting the author-pays open access model with minimal peer review and editing. Before submitting your work to an unfamiliar publisher, thoroughly assess them using checklists and resources provided in this guide. Seek feedback from colleagues and consider consulting your liaison librarian for guidance. Librarians can use the Think/Check/Submit Checklist to evaluate the quality of open access journals. While the Directory of Open Access Journals (DOAJ) is a reputable resource, it is not regularly updated. Librarians should also be cautious of predatory publishers, predatory stand-alone journals, hijacked journals, and misleading metrics. Some journals may not meet the highest editorial or technical standards but are still applying reasonable processes to their articles in good faith.

Exercise caution when considering a journal, as flaws in a publisher's processes could lead to it being labeled as predatory, even if there is no deliberate intent to deceive due to resource limitations.

Signs of a predatory journal/publisher include:

- Lack of peer review or minimal peer review process
- Solicitation of manuscripts through spam emails
- Promise of quick publication with little to no editorial oversight
- Lack of transparency in publication fees or unclear fee structures
- False claims of indexing in reputable databases
- Poorly designed or unprofessional-looking website
- Lack of clear editorial board or affiliations with reputable institutions
- Lack of clear policies on ethics, plagiarism, and conflicts of interest

Other red flags include:

- Journal title that may mislead authors or readers
- Very broad scope
- Display of unofficial impact factors
- False claims of indexing in major databases (PubMed, DOAJ)
- Lack of publisher contact information
- Unclear ownership
- Excessive email invitations for submissions
- Advertised fast publication times
- Publication of irrelevant or nonsensical articles
- Poor editing quality
- Hidden charges
- Lack of a credible editorial board
- Lack of information on journal policies

Recognizing these signs can help researchers avoid submitting their work to predatory journals. Predatory open-access publishing, also known as vanity press, is a deceptive business model that charges authors publication fees without providing legitimate editorial and publishing services. This issue has become more prevalent with the growth of online publishing and open-access journals, which has allowed for the commercialization of scientific publishing. It is important to distinguish that not all open-access journals are predatory; there are reputable ones that undergo indexing and peer review processes. Predatory journals and publishers prioritize their own interests over academic integrity, often resorting to false or misleading information, straying from best editorial practices, lacking transparency, and engaging in aggressive and indiscriminate solicitation tactics.

Examples of predatory publishers include:

1. A M Publishers
2. BioMed Research
3. Excellent Publishers

CONCLUSION

Editors should address suspected misconduct by authors, reviewers, or editorial staff in accordance with COPE guidelines. They must solicit a response from the accused and involve relevant employers or regulatory bodies as necessary. In cases involving their own staff, editors misconduct an investigation and take appropriate action. Predatory publishers, lacking peer review and imposing restrictive copyright agreements, pose a threat to researchers' reputations and careers. The "**Think. Check. Submit.**" website provides a helpful checklist for researchers to identify reputable journals.

Predatory publishers often charge authors for publication without delivering expected services such as editorial or peer review. While publication fees are common, publishers should ensure quality services in exchange. Authors submitting to questionable publishers may encounter steep withdrawal fees. These publishers are also referred to as fake, questionable, illegitimate, deceptive, or "operating in bad faith" journals.

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